

Co-Design Workshop Protocol and Facilitation Materials for Design Futures Exploration of Digital Mental Health Technologies for Young People

COST Action CA23153 - Digital Mental Health for Young People (YouthDMH)
WG3: Contextual and Early Assessment and Intervention

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Abstract

This repository contains the workshop protocol and facilitation materials developed within COST Action CA23153 Digital Mental Health for Young People (YouthDMH), Working Group 3: Contextual and Early Assessment and Intervention. The materials support the implementation of a stakeholder co-design workshop methodology informed by the Future Workshops methodology for contextual assessment and early intervention exploration in youth digital mental health. The definition which is used for contextual assessment is the following. Contextual assessment enables investigations in real-world settings and can include data collection on contextual information on environmental characteristics, the repeated assessment of symptomatology across time for analyses of within-subject processes, or the real-time data capture to minimise retrospective biases. The current set of materials includes the workshop protocol, personas, working definition cards, technology scenarios, and phase-specific activity materials used during workshop implementation. The repository aims to support methodological transparency, reproducibility, adaptation, and reuse by researchers and practitioners conducting participatory and co-design activities exploring future technologies for contextual assessment and early intervention approaches in youth digital mental health. Materials are shared under an open license to support collaborative research practices and broader methodological dissemination. The materials are intended for researchers, practitioners, and participatory design teams conducting future-oriented digital mental health research and co-design activities.

Keywords: Digital Mental Health, Young People, Contextual Assessment, Early Intervention, Design Futures, Future Workshops, Co-Design, YouthDMH, COST Action

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1. Repository Contents

This repository contains materials supporting the implementation of the co-design workshop methodology in all its phases, prior, during and after the workshop (see Figure 1 and Table 1).

Figure 1. Repository Structure and Material Organisation

Component	Description
Protocol	Workshop methodology and facilitation process
Personas	Participant personas used throughout workshop activities
Working Definitions Card	Definitions and concepts introduced and explained to participants to establish shared understanding during workshop activities.
Technology Scenarios	Scenario prompts used to facilitate discussion, reflection, and exploration of future technologies within the Design Futures activities.
Phase 1 Materials	Activity worksheet supporting Phase 1 workshop activities.
Phase 2 Materials	Activity worksheet supporting Phase 2 workshop activities.
Phase 3 Materials	Activity worksheet supporting Phase 3 workshop activities.
Post-Workshop Questionnaire	Post-session questionnaire used following workshop completion.
Supporting Documentation	Repository documentation, repository metadata, licensing information, and reuse guidance.

Table 1. Repository Components and Descriptions

2. Method overview

The workshop protocol draws on the Future Workshop methodology, originally developed by Jungk and Müllert in the 1970s to support citizen participation in decision-making processes and collaborative problem-solving around societal challenges (1). The method aims to help groups identify shared issues, generate visions of desirable futures, and explore how these futures can be realised through practical actions. The Future Workshop methodology has been adapted over time within participatory research, action research, and Human–Computer Interaction (HCI) contexts to support democratic, inclusive, and future-oriented research. The approach has been recognised as particularly valuable when working with marginalised groups and when collaboratively designing technological responses to complex challenges (2-6).

Within the YouthDMH COST Action context, the workshop protocol was developed using the Future Workshop methodology to support participatory exploration of future technologies and participatory approaches to contextual assessment and early intervention in youth digital mental health. In particular, we have adopted a vision in 4 phases plus a prior set-up phase as described in Table 2.

Phase	Phase Objective	Materials
Set-Up	To ensure all participants have provided informed consent, establish a shared understanding of key concepts, and orient participants to the workshop objectives before substantive activities begin.	Participant information sheets; Consent forms; Working Definitions Card
Phase 1: Critique	Participants identify current challenges, barriers, and frustrations based on lived experiences and contextual realities.	Personas; Technology Scenarios; Phase 1 worksheet
Phase 2: Fantasy	Participants develop aspirational and future-oriented ideas regarding ideal solutions. At this stage, participants are encouraged to move beyond practical constraints and imagine desirable future circumstances and possibilities.	Personas; Technology Scenarios; Phase 2 worksheet
Phase 3: Implementation	Participants return to practical and implementation-oriented thinking by exploring how envisioned ideas could be partially or fully realised through realistic responses, interventions, or technological approaches.	Personas; Technology Scenarios; Phase 3 worksheet
Phase 4: Close and Debrief	Participants reflect on workshop activities, provide feedback, and receive information regarding next steps and follow-up procedures.	Post-workshop questionnaire

Table 2. Workshop Phases, Objectives, and Materials

As indicated in Table 2, core workshop materials (personas, technology scenarios, and working definitions) were developed to ease collaboration throughout workshop implementation. We believe these materials can be of great help for other researchers and practitioners interested in co-creation, which is why we facilitate them within this repository for their use under CC-BY 4.0 licence. In addition to them, some other resources are needed, including post-it notes, pens and markers, and flipcharts, as described in Section 3.

3. Development of Workshop Materials

Workshop materials were developed iteratively within COST Action CA23153 YouthDMH Working Group 3 (Contextual and Early Assessment and Intervention). Materials were designed to support participatory exploration of future digital mental health technologies on contextual assessment and early intervention.

Technology scenarios were developed through exploration of the literature and review of existing technologies relevant to contextual assessment and youth digital mental health. The research team selected representative examples of existing and emerging technological approaches to facilitate discussion regarding future opportunities, challenges, and design considerations.

Personas were developed based on evidence synthesis and expert consensus across YouthDMH Cost Action working groups, to support structured discussion and future-oriented exploration during workshop activities. The two personas selected have complementary profiles, differing in age, context, and access to a mental health professional, to reflect differing potential use of contextual assessment tools.

Phase-specific materials were developed by the research team to facilitate structured discussion and participatory co-design activities across workshop phases. The templates were designed to be flexible and usable in different co-creation scenarios. When printed or displayed in a big format, they can be shared among participants (one template for all) to be the basis for hands-on physical interaction using manipulable elements such as post-its and circular stickers, allowing participants to express preferences and collaboratively construct concepts. When facilitated in a smaller format (e.g. A4), they can alternatively be handed to each participant independently for personal reflection at their own pace.

4. Citation and Reuse

To acknowledge this document or the use of the materials shared, please add the recommended citation.

Recommended citation

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Recommended reuse

- adaptation of workshop materials
- methodological reuse
- educational purposes
- participatory design activities

Please cite the repository DOI when reusing materials.

5. References

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